

Bifurcation Limits and Non-idealities Effects in a Three-phase Dynamic IPT System

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Abstract—Multiphase Dynamic Inductive Power Transfer (D-IPT) systems are capable of achieving uniform power transmission with low control complexity and high efficiency. To achieve acceptable power capabilities, D-IPT systems have to work in resonance configurations. In contrast to transformers, and due to the low coupling coefficient, the compensation is carried out separately in the primary and secondary sides. Consequently, an effect known as bifurcation or pole-splitting is created. This causes extra losses in the semiconductors because Zero Voltage Switching (ZVS) is lost. The main objective of this article is to derive the bifurcation limits for a three-phase D-IPT system. First, the meander coil configuration is introduced. Because this is a system with multiple variables, five assumptions are made to achieve close form equations. Therefore, the 36 inductance system is converted into an ideal three inductance problem. With these assumptions, the equations of the coupling, power and inductance ratio limits are obtained. Afterwards, the repercussion of these assumptions is analyzed using illustrations that depict the input impedance angle for various non-ideal conditions. Finally, a 9kW prototype is used to validate the calculations, analyzing two different operating points: incomplete ZVS and complete ZVS.

Index Terms—D-IPT, inductive power transfer, dynamic charging, meander coil, bifurcation, pole-splitting, railway transportation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Future sustainable transportation largely depends on how power electronics will manage to achieve smaller, lighter and more efficient power converter and systems. Public awareness of the environmental impact of greenhouse emissions has greatly increased over the course of the twenty-first century. However, despite efforts to turn around the situation, there is still much work to do.

One of the most promising concepts under study is Inductive Power Transfer (IPT) [1, 2], also known as wireless power transfer [3, 4] or contactless power transfer [1, 5]. New power semiconductor technologies (SiC [3, 5] and GaN [6]) have enabled the development of reasonably high switching frequencies (kHz order) in high power converters (kW order) [7], which has permitted long-known technologies, such as IPT (Tesla's patent is from 1914 [8]), to become a reality [9].

Even though the objective of IPT is to be the main charging option for electric vehicles in the future, public transportation seems to be the niche where IPT and especially dynamic-IPT (D-IPT) can be installed. Railway transportation appears to be the most realistic because the rails set the position of the vehicle. This drastically simplifies the design process because

a misalignment of one of the axis can be neglected. Moreover, the transmission coil can also be optimized. Given that trains and trams typically run the same route, the charging equipment can be optimally designed by setting the best charging points [10].

The main advantage of IPT systems in railway transportation is the opportunity to remove the pantograph, whose maintenance is expensive [11]. The pantograph suffers from friction and adverse climatology conditions. Moreover, the catenary itself could also be removed, which is another element that is exposed to friction, climatology and vandalism.

Other ways of removing these elements have been already put into practice. For instance, one solution is to endow the train with an energy storage system (ESS), batteries and ultracapacitors (UC), which could be recharged in the stops [10–12]. However, these solutions do not solve the problem of the high costs of the batteries and the infrastructure maintenance costs.

Returning to D-IPT, at first sight the full removal of the storage system seems the ideal solution. Nevertheless, the cost of installing an inductive power transmission system through all the journey seems unfeasible. In particular, it could not compete with catenaries or batteries in price. Even with less maintenance costs, railway systems can often be over 300km in length. Therefore, dynamic charging solutions could be useful during acceleration or in the places of high peak consumption (e.g. ramps). This could enable the storage system to be optimized in energy and not in power. In fact, the main power peaks would be delivered by the D-IPT charger. Furthermore, the benefit of the batteries' energy recovery feature will be kept.

Academic research regarding dynamic IPT charging has taken two clearly defined paths, as reported in [4, 13]. On the one hand, there are segmented or distributed D-IPT systems [14–16]. Here, the systems are built with concatenating stationary charging topologies, creating a charging lane. Consequently, each of the coils will be turned-on when the receiver coil (i.e. the vehicle) is placed on top of it. On the other hand, there are single coil solutions. In this solution, the transmitter coil is extended so that the receiver coil will always be within the magnetic field [17]. Therefore, the transmitter coil will always deliver power independently of where the receiver coil is placed.

Depending on the chosen solution, in addition to the efficiency and power density targets, different challenges have

to be faced. With a segmented solution, the sizes of the transmitter coils are smaller. This means that the inductance value will be smaller and, consequently, the voltage must also withstand this. However, the movement of the vehicle makes the control very complex because the equivalent circuit keeps changing constantly. The control must be very accurate to manage these changes and the circuit must be designed to operate in the worst case. With this configuration, at the present time, the power densities and efficiencies are identical to the static systems, with efficiencies of around 90%, and most of the publications are focused on implementing different control strategies [18–20]. With a single coil solution, the control becomes simpler but the large size of the transmitter coils complicates the voltage insulation and the losses also increase. The efficiency at the current state is around 70%, with an air-gap of 10cm [17, 21].

Multi-phase meander coils have been used to improve the deficiencies of single coils [13, 22]. By combining their magnetic fields, the output power can be controlled to deliver constant power to the receiver coils [23, 24]. Consequently, the large voltages through the inductors are reduced because each coil will carry only part of the total power.

Despite the studies and patents [25–27] related to meander coils, the problem of bifurcation phenomena and the limits (already analyzed for single-phase systems [28, 29]) are still to be determined for multi-phase systems. In addition, the effect of non-idealities has not yet been reported in literature.

The bifurcation phenomena is of major concern as directly affects the switching conditions of the semiconductors (described in section III-C of this work). In IPT systems, also in other resonant systems, the name bifurcation or ‘pole-splitting’ is given to the effect where three resonant frequencies appear instead of just one, due to the interaction between the primary and the secondary LC resonant tanks [30–32]. Due to this effect, even having both LC tanks tuned at the same frequency, extra resonant frequencies appear slightly above and below the tuning point. As a consequence, zero-voltage-switching (ZVS) is lost and efficiency is reduced.

Therefore, the objective of this article is to derive the bifurcation limits and acknowledge the effects of non-idealities to serve as a reference for future multi-phase IPT designs. For that purpose, in the first section, to better understand the system, the working principle and the model of a three-phase meander coil are explained. In the second section, the bifurcation theory is introduced and the analogy from single-phase to multi-phase system is carried out. In this work, these limits will be obtained for series-series compensation. In the third section, the effects of non-idealities such as resonance variation, cross-coupling and wire resistance are analyzed. Finally, in the fourth section, the theory and limits are validated in a 9kW system and a bifurcated system is adapted by changing the resonance of the secondary side coil.

II. PRINCIPLE OF OPERATION OF MEANDER COILS

Fig. 1 illustrates the three-phase D-IPT system. Three meander type transmitter/primary coils are placed on the ground (labeled A, B and C). Whereas, three square type

Fig. 1: Three-phase meander type coil configuration. The magnetic field created in the cut-plane by a single-phase is depicted in Fig. 2. The receivers are placed in the x-y plane, so the perpendicular field is B_z .

Fig. 2: Magnetic field in the z direction, denoted as B_z , for $i_A = \hat{i}$. The blue color or N letter indicates a negative field value. Whereas, the red color and the P letter indicates a positive field magnitude. The superimposed black line represents the mutual inductance for different receiver positions and for a certain coil separation.

receiver/secondary coils are mounted in the vehicle (labeled a, b and c). For the current analysis, the x coordinate will be the moving direction of the receiver coils.

The magnetic field produced by a single meander type IPT coil is depicted in Fig. 2. Considering that the current flows in and out of the y axis, the magnetic field will be created in the x-z plane.

According to Faraday’s law, a magnetic field perpendicularly crossing a coil will induce a voltage. In an electric circuit, this effect is represented by a mutual inductance. For the case under study, because the receiver coils are placed in the x-y plane, see Fig. 1, the perpendicular field will be B_z . Moving along x, and making the integral of B_z over the current, we get the mutual inductance drawn in Fig. 2. As can be observed, this mutual inductance has a sinusoidal shape. Therefore, it can be described by

$$M(z, \lambda, x) = \hat{M}(z, \lambda) \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda} x\right) \quad (1)$$

where λ is the geometric period of the coil and $\hat{M}(z, \lambda)$ is the peak mutual inductance that depends on the air-gap z and the coil period. This peak value is achieved when the center

of the receiver coil is located in the middle of two wires, see Fig. 2, and can be obtained by FEM simulations.

It can be observed that when using a single transmitter and single receiver coil, there are positions where there is no field linked (i.e. no power is transmitted). For this particular example, where $\lambda = 200\text{mm}$, these gaps are given at 0, 100mm, 200mm, 300mm and 400mm. To solve this problem, extra phases are used.

A. Geometrical phase shift

Adding extra phases overcomes the problem of ‘field gaps’. However, in the same way that the field is linked with the receiver coil, neighboring transmitter coils will induce a voltage in each other. The name given to this effect is cross-coupling, which is also represented with a mutual inductance. The value of the cross-coupling inductance is constant because the relative position between transmitters (also between receivers) is always equal.

To have a balanced system, the cross-coupling mutual inductances have to be as equal as possible; that is, $M_{A,B} = M_{B,C} = M_{C,A}$ and $M_{a,b} = M_{b,c} = M_{c,a}$. Because the mutual inductance depends on the position, for the three-phase case under study, the same distance can only be achieved if the phase shift among transmitters and among receivers is 120° . Note that considering the scenario depicted in Fig. 1, the coupling between a and c—that is, $M_{a,c}$ —will be smaller than $M_{a,b}$ and $M_{b,c}$ as the distance is larger. However, as will be shown in Section V, the cross-coupling between receiver coils is so small that it can be neglected.

Considering a phase shift of 120° , the mutual inductances between transmitter and receiver phases are described by

$$\begin{aligned} M_{A,a} &= M_{B,b} = M_{C,c} = \hat{M} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}x\right) \\ M_{A,b} &= M_{B,c} = M_{C,a} = \hat{M} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}x + \frac{2\pi}{3}\right) \\ M_{A,c} &= M_{B,a} = M_{C,b} = \hat{M} \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{\lambda}x - \frac{2\pi}{3}\right). \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

B. Inductance matrix

The equivalent matrix of a three-phase D-IPT system is presented in (3). This matrix can be divided in three main groups: the transmitter inductance (4a), which gathers the self inductances of each meander coil and the cross-coupling between transmitters; the receiver inductance (4b), which is similar to the previous case but with the receiver coils; and finally the mutual inductance itself (5), with the combinations of all mutual inductances between transmitter and receiver coils.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \vec{v}_{L,A} \\ \vec{v}_{L,B} \\ \vec{v}_{L,C} \\ \vec{v}_{L,a} \\ \vec{v}_{L,b} \\ \vec{v}_{L,c} \end{bmatrix} = j\omega \begin{bmatrix} L_{ABC,ABC} & M_{abc,ABC} \\ M_{ABC,abc} & L_{abc,abc} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \vec{i}_{L,A} \\ \vec{i}_{L,B} \\ \vec{i}_{L,C} \\ \vec{i}_{L,a} \\ \vec{i}_{L,b} \\ \vec{i}_{L,c} \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 3: Peak induced voltage depending on the position of the receiver coil and the angle of the current and $\hat{M} = 1$ and $\hat{i} = 1$. With a phase shift of 120° constant induced voltage is obtained.

where the self inductances matrix are

$$L_{ABC,ABC} = \begin{bmatrix} L_{A,A} & M_{B,A} & M_{C,A} \\ M_{A,B} & L_{B,B} & M_{C,B} \\ M_{A,C} & M_{B,C} & L_{C,C} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4a)$$

$$L_{abc,abc} = \begin{bmatrix} L_{a,a} & M_{b,a} & M_{c,a} \\ M_{a,b} & L_{b,b} & M_{c,b} \\ M_{a,c} & M_{b,c} & L_{c,c} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4b)$$

and the mutual inductances matrix are

$$M_{abc,ABC} = \begin{bmatrix} M_{a,A} & M_{b,A} & M_{c,A} \\ M_{a,B} & M_{b,B} & M_{c,B} \\ M_{a,C} & M_{b,C} & M_{c,C} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

$$M_{ABC,abc} = \begin{bmatrix} M_{A,a} & M_{B,a} & M_{C,a} \\ M_{A,b} & M_{B,b} & M_{C,b} \\ M_{A,c} & M_{B,c} & M_{C,c} \end{bmatrix}.$$

where $\vec{i}_{L,A}$, $\vec{i}_{L,B}$, $\vec{i}_{L,C}$, $\vec{i}_{L,a}$, $\vec{i}_{L,b}$, $\vec{i}_{L,c}$ is the current circulating through each coil and $\vec{v}_{L,A}$, $\vec{v}_{L,B}$, $\vec{v}_{L,C}$, $\vec{v}_{L,a}$, $\vec{v}_{L,b}$, $\vec{v}_{L,c}$ are the voltages at the terminals of each coil.

C. Electrical phase shift

If we consider that $\vec{i}_{L,A} = \vec{i}_{L,B} = \vec{i}_{L,C}$, then it is clear that $\vec{v}_{L,a}$, $\vec{v}_{L,b}$ and $\vec{v}_{L,c}$ will be zero for all positions, the sum of (2) is zero. Therefore, a phase shift is also required in the currents.

Fig. 3 illustrates the induced voltage peak value for current phase shift of 0° , 60° , 120° and 180° . The phases are connected in a star connection. So $\vec{i}_{L,A} + \vec{i}_{L,B} + \vec{i}_{L,C} = 0$ and $\vec{i}_{L,a} + \vec{i}_{L,b} + \vec{i}_{L,c} = 0$ are fulfilled. It can be observed that using a phase shift of 120° , the peak value of the induced voltage is constant for all receiver positions. This demonstrates that constant power transmission can be achieved with a three-phase meander coil configuration. It can also be observed that the induced voltage is 1.5 times bigger than what a single-phase will produce (in this illustration $\hat{M} = 1$, $\lambda = 1$ and $\hat{i} = 1$ is used).

Fig. 4: Three-phase D-IPT system with series-series compensation.

III. BIFURCATION LIMITS IN IDEAL THREE-PHASE D-IPT SYSTEMS

As observed in the previous section, a three-phase D-IPT system has 36 inductances that need to be calculated, where 18 depend on the position of the receiver coil. Typically, these values are obtained by Finite Element Method (FEM) simulations [33, 34], which slows the designing process. To speed up the process, designers typically make some assumptions that do not drastically affect the outcome.

The first objective of this section is to describe the simplifications that have been considered. Consequently, the simplified equations of the three-phase D-IPT will be obtained. The second objective of this section is to explain the impact of the bifurcation in the performance of the system and to obtain its limits. For this purpose, the procedure of the single-phase IPT [28] is translated to the three-phase case.

A. Three-phase series-series compensated system

In section I, it has been stated that the niche where dynamic IPT can be installed in the near future is railway transportation. Fig. 4 depicts the circuit of an inductive charging system for railway equipment. The primary or transmitter side, which is located in the ground, is supplied by an active inverter. Whereas, the secondary or receiver part, which is installed in the vehicle, is connected to a diode bridge. With this particular configuration, the power can only be transmitted from the primary to the secondary side.

Unlike transformers, due to the low coupling values that exhibit D-IPT systems, even though power could be transferred from the primary to the secondary side, resonant topologies are mandatory to ensure acceptable power capabilities and efficiencies. In the literature, four compensation topologies are the most extended due to their simplicity, which are series-series, series-parallel, parallel-series and parallel-parallel. The first term corresponds to the primary side compensation whereas the second term corresponds to the secondary side compensation.

In this article, the series-series compensation is going to be analyzed. Usually, in traction applications the primary side is connected to a voltage source with an imposed voltage (V_{in}), typically the grid/catenary or a power factor corrector (PFC). The secondary side is also connected to a voltage source (V_{out}), a DC/DC or a battery pack. Therefore, the D-IPT system behaves as a current source at both sides (unless an extra inductor is added), which is only achieved with a series-series compensation. At this point, it has to be mentioned that, as detailed in [28], other compensation topologies also suffer from bifurcation, and the same holds true for multi-phase IPT systems. For the sake of clarity and brevity, in this article only series-series compensation is analyzed. Nonetheless, the same procedure can be used in other compensations, first the input impedance must be obtained and afterwards the zero angles must be found.

B. Simplifications

For the design of D-IPT systems, the following five assumptions are considered:

- 1) The system is balanced. The transmitter phases have the same self inductance L_T and the receiver phases have the same inductance L_R . In addition, the current through transmitter/receiver coils is equal.
- 2) There is no cross-coupling among transmitter nor among receiver coils.
- 3) The coils are ideal conductors and there is no wire resistance.
- 4) Both resonant tanks are perfectly tuned to the same resonance frequency.
- 5) The polarization voltage of the diodes is zero.

With assumptions 1) and 2), matrices (4a) and (4b) are simplified to a identity matrix multiplied by L_T and L_R respectively. In addition, knowing from Fig. 3 that the induced voltage is 1.5 bigger for the three-phase than a single phase system, also (5) can be converted into a identity matrix, in this case multiplied by $3/2\hat{M}$. Being all the matrices identity matrices entails that each of the phases can be analyzed independently. So, basically, the 36 inductances problem has been reduced to a 3 inductances problem, as all phases are considered equal, which basically is similar to a single phase IPT. Finally, with assumptions 3), 4), 5) and considering a series-series compensation the equivalent single-phase equations are

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{v}_{L,T} &= j \left(\frac{\omega^2 - \omega_0^2}{\omega} \right) L_T \vec{i}_{L,T} - j\omega \frac{3}{2} \hat{M} \vec{i}_{L,R} \\ j\omega \frac{3}{2} \hat{M} \vec{i}_{L,T} &= \left(R_{AC} + j \left(\frac{\omega^2 - \omega_0^2}{\omega} \right) L_R \right) \vec{i}_{L,R}. \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where $R_{AC} = 6/\pi^2 \cdot V_{DC}^2/P_{out}$ is the equivalent load.

C. Bifurcation effects: Switching losses

The working frequency of IPT systems is typically between 20–200kHz, so MOSFETs are the first choice [35]. As stated previously, thanks to the development of semiconductors with wide-band-gap materials (SiC and GaN), high frequency switching is now achievable in high power applications. In

Fig. 5: Switching transition from S_2 to S_1 of a bridge leg. (a) S_1 conduction interval. (b) Blanking time, depending on the output current (i_{out}) the energy between the output capacitors is shifted or not. If the current is too low, part of the energy is still in $C_{oss,1}$, thus ZVS is not achieved. (c) S_2 conduction interval.

these systems, to further improve the efficiency, zero voltage switching (ZVS) is preferred because turn-off losses are much lower than turn-on losses [35]. In [36] a thorough analysis of ZVS is described. To achieve a full soft switching condition, the system has to work in the inductive zone with enough current to discharge the output capacitance C_{oss} of the MOSFET.

Fig. 5 depicts a switching transition from S_2 to S_1 . The transition is as follows. Before t_1 , the semiconductor S_2 is conducting and the counterpart output capacitance $C_{oss,1}$ is charged to $V_{1,DC}$. When the current is close to zero (must be working in inductive zone), the semiconductor is turned off at t_1 . Then, between t_1 and t_2 , all the switches are open and the current flows freely between the output capacitances. This current discharges $C_{oss,1}$ and transfers the energy to $C_{oss,2}$. If the inductive energy is high enough, then the voltage of $C_{oss,2}$ will reach $V_{1,DC}$ before t_2 , depicted in blue in Figure 5. However, if the current is too low, when S_1 is turned on in t_2 , then the voltage in $C_{oss,1}$ will be lower and it will suddenly rise, creating a high current spike through S_1 . Finally, after t_2 , the current will circulate through S_1 , while $C_{oss,1}$ is charged to $V_{1,DC}$.

In resonant systems, inductive behavior is typically achieved by working slightly above the resonance frequency. However, in systems with more than one resonant tank (e.g. IPT) this statement is not always true. As shown in single-phase literature [28, 35], an IPT system can have a capacitive behavior

above the resonance frequency. If this is the case, then it is said that the system is bifurcated or has pole-splitting. Therefore, ideally, it is better not to have bifurcation.

D. Bifurcation limit

To know if the system is working in a capacitive or inductive zone, the angle of the input impedance ϕ is used. If $\phi > 0$, then the system is working in an inductive zone; whereas if $\phi < 0$, then the system is in a capacitive zone. The input impedance is the relation between the primary side voltage $\vec{v}_{L,T}$ and current $\vec{i}_{L,T}$. To know if there is bifurcation, the number of times that $\phi = 0$ has to be checked. This angle is zero if the imaginary part of the input impedance is also zero (i.e. the system has a purely resistive behavior). So, defining the inductance ratio χ as

$$\chi = \frac{L_R}{L_T}, \quad (7)$$

the imaginary part of the input impedance is

$$\Im(Z_{in}) = \frac{(\omega^2 - \omega_0^2) L_T}{\omega} \cdot T_{SS} \quad (8)$$

where

$$T_{SS} = \frac{\overbrace{(\omega^2 - \omega_0^2)^2 \chi^2 L_T^2 + R_{AC}^2 \omega^2 - \chi \left(\omega^2 \frac{3}{2} \hat{M} \right)^2}^{\text{Bifurcation limit}}}{(\omega^2 - \omega_0^2)^2 \chi^2 L_T^2 + \omega^2 R_{AC}^2}. \quad (9)$$

In this equation, the imaginary part is always zero if $\omega = \omega_0$ is fulfilled. However, there is also another condition when this occurs, which is highlighted in (9). These extra zero crossings are actually the pole-splitting, and the limit is given when these term is also zero when $\omega = \omega_0$. Therefore, defining the coupling coefficient as

$$k = \frac{\hat{M}}{\sqrt{L_T L_R}} = \frac{\hat{M}}{\sqrt{\chi} L_T} \quad (10)$$

substituting \hat{M} and replacing R_{AC} we get

$$\left(\frac{6}{\pi^2} \frac{V_{2,DC}^2}{P_{out}} \right)^2 \omega_0^2 - \left(\omega_0^2 \frac{3}{2} \chi k L_T \right)^2 = 0. \quad (11)$$

Solving this equation, the maximum power that can be transmitted without bifurcation is calculated

$$P_{out,lim} = \frac{4}{\pi^2} \frac{V_{2,DC}^2}{\omega_0 \chi L_T k}. \quad (12)$$

Fig. 6 depicts the angle of the input impedance over the f/f_0 ratio for three different output powers. Once the limit is exceeded, more zero crossings appear.

If the power is a fixed value, rearranging equation (12), the maximum coupling coefficient can be calculated

$$k_{lim} = \frac{4}{\pi^2} \frac{V_{2,DC}^2}{\omega_0 \chi L_T P_{out}}. \quad (13)$$

During the design process, this value cannot be exceeded. Fig. 7 represents the input impedance over the f/f_0 ratio for three different coupling coefficient. The same conclusion can be obtained here: if the coupling coefficient exceeds (13), then pole-splitting occurs.

Fig. 6: Input impedance angle vs. frequency for various power transmission levels.

Fig. 7: Input impedance angle vs. frequency for various coupling coefficients.

IV. NON IDEALITIES EFFECTS

In the previous section, new bifurcation limits have been obtained for the three-phase D-IPT case. However, to reach those limits, some assumptions are necessary. In this section, the impact of those assumptions will be studied. Because a close form equation is hardly achievable, for sake of clarity and brevity, the analysis is going to be carried out by evaluating figures that will depict the input impedance angle over the f/f_0 ratio. These figures have been obtained numerically by solving matrix (3). All the calculations are carried out considering that the ideal case is working in the limit of pole-splitting; that is, under (12) or (13).

A. Effect of receiver cross-coupling

Fig. 8, depicts the input impedance for receiver cross-coupling coefficients k_R that vary from -0.4 to 0.4. Note that negative couplings or negative mutual inductances represent that the current is being created in the opposite direction of the reference. The cross-coupling coefficient of the receiver coils is calculated with

$$k_R = \frac{M_{a,a}}{L_{a,a}}. \quad (14)$$

Fig. 8: Input impedance angle vs. f/f_0 ratio for various receiver cross-coupling coefficients.

Fig. 9: Input impedance angle vs. f/f_0 ratio for various transmitter cross-coupling coefficients.

It can be observed that if the receiver cross-coupling coefficient is negative pole-splitting appears. Whereas, for positive values, the system is further from being bifurcated. As will be demonstrated in the next section, the cross-coupling value for the receiver coils is negative but very low, around 1%. Therefore, it can be said that the coupling among receivers can be neglected. Finally, one last aspect that can be observed in Fig. 8 is that at perfect resonant point all waveforms match. Therefore, during the design process neglecting the receiver cross-coupling is admissible.

B. Effect of transmitter cross-coupling

Likewise, Fig. 9 depicts the angle of the input impedance for transmitter cross-coupling coefficients -0.4 to 0.4. For this second case, the cross-coupling coefficient is defined as

$$k_T = \frac{M_{A,A}}{L_{A,A}}. \quad (15)$$

It can be observed that the cross-coupling of the transmitter coil has the opposite effect to the previous one; that is, for positive cross-coupling coefficient values pole-splitting appears. Whereas for negative values the system is less bifurcated. As previously mentioned, the cross-coupling values are typically

Fig. 10: Input impedance angle vs. f/f_0 ratio for various receiver quality factors.

negative, therefore the cross-coupling among transmitter coils is beneficial to achieve ZVS. This means that if an ideal D-IPT is free of pole-splitting, then the real case will be the same.

C. Effect of receiver wire resistance

Following the analysis, for the study of the effect of wire resistances, the quality factor of the coil Q is going to be used. This method is similar to the procedure presented in [28]. The quality factor of the receiver coil Q_R is defined as

$$Q_R = \frac{\omega_0 L_R}{R_R} \quad (16)$$

Fig. 10 depicts the input impedance angle for $Q_R = 1, 10, 100$ and ∞ . For all cases, the transmitter coil is considered an ideal conductor; that is, $Q_T = \infty$. It can be observed that reducing the quality of the receiver coil makes the system less bifurcated. A lossless system is free of pole-splitting if the receiver losses are considered. Nonetheless, it must be mentioned that is better to have higher quality factors because the efficiency will be higher.

D. Effect of transmitter wire resistance

The same procedure is applied for the analysis of the transmitter wire resistance. In this case, the quality factor is defined as

$$Q_T = \frac{\omega_0 L_T}{R_T} \quad (17)$$

Fig. 11 depicts the angle of the input impedance for $Q_T = 1, 10, 100$ and ∞ . Here, the receiver coil is considered an ideal conductor; that is, $Q_R = \infty$. Analyzing the result, it can be observed that the quality factor of the transmitter coil has no effect in the bifurcation phenomena. For all the solutions, there is only one zero-crossing point. In addition, close to the resonance frequency, the waveforms are identical. Therefore, Q_T will not have an effect in the bifurcation limit; therefore, considering the transmitter coil ideal is also valid for the limit calculation.

Up to this point, the simplifications (all related to the inductive link) that have been made have not altered the limit of bifurcation. The next two factors are more closely related to the compensation itself.

Fig. 11: Input impedance angle vs. f/f_0 ratio for various transmitter quality factors.

Fig. 12: Input impedance angle vs. f/f_0 ratio for various receiver resonance frequencies.

E. Effect of a mis-tuned receiver

Typically, when a coil is mounted, there are slight differences between the simulated/estimated values and the real one. However, in most cases the resonant capacitors are selected with this simulated/estimated value. The same holds true if the capacitance value is not exactly the same as the selected one; for example, due to tolerances. The direct effect of these deviations is that the resonant frequency will not be exactly the chosen one. Thus, its effect in the bifurcation must be analyzed.

Instead of using the absolute deviation, for this study the displacement over the resonance frequency is going to be analyzed. Fig. 12 depicts the input impedance angle for receiver resonance f_{0R} deviations that go from 80% to 120% from the ideal case (i.e from f_0).

It can be observed that going in either direction frees the system of pole-splitting. However, the response is not equal. If the resonance frequency of the receiver is smaller than the ideal ($f_{0R} < f_0$), then the overall resonance frequency will increase (zero crossing at higher frequencies). Therefore, if the system is switching at f_0 , then it will be working in a capacitive zone. At this point, not only ZVS is not achieved but the switching losses will also be increased due to turn-on

Fig. 13: Input impedance angle vs. f/f_0 ratio for various transmitter resonance frequencies.

losses. In contrast, if the resonance frequency is larger than the ideal ($f_{0R} > f_0$), then the overall resonance frequency will decrease (zero crossings at lower frequencies). In this second case, working at f_0 , the system will be at a positive angle (inductive zone) and will have better switching conditions.

F. Effect of mis-tuned transmitter

Finally, the effect of a mis-tuned transmitter f_{0T} is analysed. Fig. 13 illustrates this state. The same effect as Fig. 12 can be appreciated—all the solutions are free of pole-splitting. However, for this case, if $f_{0T} > f_0$ and the inverter is working at f_0 , then the switching will be carried out in capacitive conditions, increasing the losses. Whereas, if $f_{0T} < f_0$, then the system will become inductive.

Special care has to be paid to the mis-tuned transmitter effect. As can be observed, the effect is much more pronounced than for the mis-tuned receiver. Note that for $f_{0T} = 0.9f_0$ at $f = f_0$, the angle of the input impedance is 60° . This means that with a small change, the angle is drastically varied.

The main conclusion of this analysis is that the limits can be calculated using the ideal equation. Then, depending on the deviation of the real coil with the designed one, if necessary the resonance frequency can be modified to achieve soft switching conditions.

V. EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

To validate the limits derived in Section III, experimental tests are carried out in a 9kW prototype with the specifications given in Table I.

One of the main challenges of dynamic chargers is achieving sufficient peak mutual inductance. Given some size limits, the only way of increasing this value is to add more turns, either to the transmitter or to the receiver coils (note that if the dimensions are not changed the coupling coefficient remains equal). This enables the the mutual inductance to increase proportionally, as given by

$$M = k\sqrt{N_T^2 L_{T,1} N_R^2 L_{R,1}} = kN_T N_R \sqrt{L_{T,1} L_{R,1}} \quad (18)$$

Electric Specifications

Parameter	Variable	Value
Max. input voltage	$V_{1,DC}$	520 V
Max. output voltage	$V_{2,DC}$	600 V
Switching frequency	f_0	100kHz
Output power	P_{out}	9 kW
Ideal values		
Load resistance	$R_{2,DC}$	40 Ω
Peak mutual inductance	M	22.36 μ H
Transmitter self inductance (FEM)	L_T	100 μ H
Receiver self inductance (FEM)	L_R	340 μ H
Coupling coefficient (FEM)	k	0.12

TABLE I: Specifications of the 9kW prototype.

where $L_{T,1}$ and $L_{R,1}$ are the self inductances with a single turn and N_T and N_R are the number of turns of the transmitter and receiver coils, respectively.

However, both the mutual inductance and also the inherent resistor of the coils increase, which reduces the efficiency. Introducing a single turn in the meander coil is more penalising than in the receiver square coils because the length is much longer. In addition, because the system is working in resonance, the voltage that must withstand the coil will be quadratic to the number of turns. Therefore, for this particular case, the secondary side is mounted with the maximum number of turns that can be introduced. Whereas, the meander coil has the necessary number of turns to achieve the desired mutual inductance.

The coupling and power limits are as follows

$$k_{lim,ideal} = \frac{4}{\pi^2} \frac{V_{2,DC}^2}{\omega_0 L_R P_{out}} = 0.076, \quad (19a)$$

$$P_{lim,ideal} = \frac{4}{\pi^2} \frac{V_{2,DC}^2}{\omega_0 L_R k} = 5.7kW. \quad (19b)$$

These values are below the limits, so bifurcation is expected. Nevertheless, as previously shown, due to the transmitter couplings or receiver losses, the system can be free of pole-splitting. If this is the case, then the resonant tank can be tuned to f_0 , otherwise the frequency of the primary side has to be reduced.

A. Characterisation

Table II summarises the measurement of the inductances (self and cross-coupling) and resistances of the six coils. Fig. 14 depicts all of the mutual inductance combinations. In this figure, the lines represent the FEM results, whereas the dots represent the measurements. Because the procedure presented in [22] has been used to characterise the mutual inductance, only absolute values were measured. The empty circles of Fig. 14 are not the exact measured value but its negative. The results show that the peak mutual inductance is approximately 20 μ H, which is only 1% less than the desired value. In addition, the 120° phase shift can be also observed. This measurements have been carried out using the Agilent 4285A RLC meter.

Even though a 40 Ω resistor has been used, due to tolerances, when measuring a resistive value of 39 Ω has been obtained.

Characterisation

Parameter	Variable	Value
Transmitter self inductance	$L_{A,A}$	95.30 μH
	$L_{B,B}$	93.50 μH
	$L_{C,C}$	95.05 μH
Receiver self inductance	$L_{a,a}$	355 μH
	$L_{b,b}$	353.3 μH
	$L_{c,c}$	354.5 μH
Transmitter mutual inductance	$M_{A,B}$	-16.83 μH
	$M_{B,C}$	-18.1 μH
	$M_{C,A}$	-16.45 μH
Receiver mutual inductance	$M_{a,b}$	-5.5 μH
	$M_{b,c}$	-5.4 μH
	$M_{c,a}$	0.0 μH
Transmitter wire resistance	$R_{A,A}$	0.29 Ω
	$R_{B,B}$	0.31 Ω
	$R_{C,C}$	0.3 Ω
Receiver wire resistance	$R_{a,a}$	0.64 Ω
	$R_{b,b}$	0.63 Ω
	$R_{c,c}$	0.61 Ω
Load resistance	$R_{2,DC}$	39 Ω

TABLE II: 9kW prototype measured inductances and resistances.

Fig. 14: 9kW prototype measured mutual inductances.

Therefore, if there were no losses in the system, then the transferred power would be slightly bigger than 9kW. The values of the self inductances of the receiver coil are also slightly higher to the predefined values.

The measured resistive value is low, corresponding to a quality factor of

$$Q_T = \frac{\omega_0 (L_{A,B} + L_{B,C} + L_{C,A}) / 3}{(R_{A,A} + R_{B,B} + R_{C,C}) / 3} = 198.16, \quad (20)$$

for the transmitter coil and

$$Q_R = \frac{\omega_0 (L_{a,b} + L_{b,c} + L_{c,a}) / 3}{(R_{a,a} + R_{b,b} + R_{c,c}) / 3} = 355.2, \quad (21)$$

for the receiver coil. Consequently, looking at Fig. 10 and Fig. 11, it can be seen that they will not have an effect.

The cross-coupling coefficient of the transmitter is

$$k_T = \frac{(M_{A,B} + M_{B,C} + M_{C,A}) / 3}{(L_{A,A} + L_{B,B} + L_{C,C}) / 3} = -0.181, \quad (22)$$

whereas for the receiver is

$$k_R = \frac{(M_{a,b} + M_{b,c} + M_{c,a}) / 3}{(L_{a,a} + L_{b,b} + L_{c,c}) / 3} = -0.01. \quad (23)$$

Fig. 16: Input impedance angle vs. f/f_0 ratio. The resonance frequency has been reduced from 100kHz (grey) to 96.5kHz (black).

So, even though there is cross-coupling between transmitter coils, it is not very high. Considering Fig. 9, it can be seen that with a $k_T = 0.2$ there is no major change. Regarding k_R , and as previously mentioned, due to the proposed geometry, the cross-coupling coefficient of the receivers is practically null; therefore, it will have no effect. Therefore, the design system is expected to have bifurcation.

Fig. 15 depicts the angle of the input impedance for the measured values considering an ideal compensation (ideal values of the capacitors).

As anticipated, the system is slightly bifurcated. As shown in Section IV (Fig. 13), to solve this problem, the capacitance values have to be selected in such a way that the resonance frequency of the transmitter side is reduced. In particular, this resonance frequency is reduced to 96.5kHz (note that is less than 4%), which gives the response depicted in Fig. 16.

It can be seen that the system is no longer bifurcated. However, if the switching frequency is kept to 100kHz (triangle point), then there is not enough current to fully discharge the output capacitance, see Fig. 17, so ZVS is not fully completed.

One option to solve this problem is to further reduce the resonance frequency. In this case, the switching frequency has been increased to 104kHz (star point), where the angle is bigger. This enables enough current to be obtained and ZVS

Fig. 17: Working at 100kHz, triangle point in Fig. 16, even though the system is working in an inductive zone, there is not enough current to obtain ZVS.

Fig. 18: Working at 104kHz, star point in Fig. 16, the system is working in an inductive zone and there is enough current to obtain ZVS.

is achieved, see Fig. 18.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this article, close form equations that calculate the bifurcation phenomena limits have been obtained for an ideal three-phase D-IPT system. First, the working principles of a meander coil D-IPT system have been thoroughly described. It has been demonstrated that constant power transmission can be achieved throughout a charging lane, which enables dynamic wireless powering with simple control. Afterwards, the impact of having a bifurcated system has been described, if the system is moved to a capacitive zone, the losses in the semiconductors considerably increase as zero-voltage-switching is lost. Apart from that, thanks to the proposed assumptions, the 36 inductances problem has been reduced to a three inductances problem, which considerably reduces the simulation time while maintaining the accuracy. In addition, for the three-phase IPT systems, it is shown that the required mutual inductance is $3/2$ times smaller. Once the pole-splitting limits have been derived, the repercussion of the initial assumptions in a complete system have been evaluated. It has been demonstrated that the cross-coupling of the transmitter coils and the receiver wire losses are beneficial regarding bifurcation. It has also been demonstrated that the resonance frequency of one side of the inductive link can be adapted

to achieve a bifurcation-less system. Finally, all the theory has been validated in a 9kW/100kHz experimental prototype. Our measurements confirm that, even in an initially bifurcated system, ZVS above resonance frequency can be achieved by adapting the resonance frequency of either resonant tank. Summarizing, the theory presented in this work serves as initial guideline for designing multi-phase dynamic IPT chargers.

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